

1) Definition and characteristics of the moist-air entropy and « theta-s » θ_s

(“Tutorial” written in French in 2022 and translated in English in 2026 by Pascal Marquet)

Since 2011, it is easy to study the entropy of the moist-air atmosphere, considered as a mixture in varying proportions of dry air, water vapor, liquid water, and ice. This study was made possible thanks, on the one hand, to a precise calculation as required by thermodynamics and by applying the third law of thermodynamics, and on the other hand, to the definition of a new potential temperature noted θ_s defined as is common practice in meteorology.

The most general formula is:

$$\theta_s = \theta \exp\left(-\frac{L_v q_l + L_s q_i}{c_{pd} T}\right) \exp(\Lambda_r q_t) \times \left(\frac{T}{T_r}\right)^{\lambda q_t} \left(\frac{p}{p_r}\right)^{-\kappa \delta q_t} \left(\frac{r_r}{r_v}\right)^{\gamma q_t} \frac{(1 + \eta r_v)^{\kappa(1 + \delta q_t)}}{(1 + \eta r_r)^{\kappa \delta q_t}} \times (H_l)^{\gamma q_l} (H_i)^{\gamma q_i} \left(\frac{T_l}{T}\right)^{c_l q_l / c_{pd}} \left(\frac{T_i}{T}\right)^{c_i q_i / c_{pd}}$$

with the following reasonable approximation :

$$\theta_s \approx \theta \exp\left(-\frac{L_v q_l + L_s q_i}{c_{pd} T}\right) \exp(\Lambda_r q_t)$$

where $\Lambda_r = 5.869 \pm 0.003$ (close to 6) represents the impact of the third law of thermodynamics (absolute reference entropies for dry air and water vapour) and $q_t = q_v + q_l + q_i$ is the “total water content” ;

and thus with the crude approximation for clear-sky conditions ($q_l = q_i = 0$):

$$\theta_s \approx \theta \times (1 + 6 q_v)$$

The most complex formulation for θ_s (boxed in blue) is suitable for the most precise numerical calculations, while the simpler ones (boxed in red) simply show that, almost as with the other moist-air variables θ'_w and θ_e , entropy and θ_s are larger for larger values of the dry-air potential temperature (θ) and for larger values of the vapor content (q_v).

Conversely, isentropic regions (i.e. with the same value of θ_s) are either those where both θ and q_v are constant (conservative variables), or those where the variations of θ_s and q_v have opposite signs and can compensate each other via the coefficient "5.869" close to 6. It should be noted that this coefficient is smaller than the one $L_v / (c_{pd} T)$ close to 9 used in the approximate formulation of θ_e , which explains why θ_e cannot represent the moist-air entropy and isentropic surfaces, which can only be evaluated with θ_s .

It appears that the moist-air entropy measured with this variable θ_s has singular, new and interesting properties which have been documented in various articles by P. Marquet (from 2011 to 2022), as well as in the M2 stage report of E. Blot (2013), where many properties in “forecaster” mode were studied by comparing maps and vertical sections of θ_s with those obtained for the variables more familiar to forecasters such as θ'_w and/or θ_e .

In particular, it is shown that the "air mass" and “fronts analyses” aspects are better seen with θ_s in the lower layers of the atmosphere, with also innovative aspects for the associated potential vorticity quantity "PV(θ_s)", where moderate negative zones of PV(θ_s) located on the low-levels fronts seem to correspond to regions of heavy precipitation associated with "slantwise convection" or "symmetric instability" (Marquet, 2014).

References about the definition and studies of the moist-air entropy:

- * My research activities (since 1982-83 up to now) are described on : <https://sites.google.com/view/pascal-marquet/>
- * The 2011 QJRMS paper by Pascal Marquet about θ_S : <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.787/abstract>
with the coloured version on arXiv : <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.1097>
- * The 2013 paper written with Jean-François Geleyn about the Brunt-Väisälä frequency:
<http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.1957/abstract> <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>
- * The 2013 M2 report by Etienne Blot about the use and interest of θ_S and $PV(\theta_S)$ for forecasters :
<https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>
- * The 2014 QJRMS paper by Marquet about the potential-vorticity quantity $PV(\theta_S)$:
<http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/qj.2182/abstract> and the arXiv version : <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2006>
- * The 2015 Chapter written with Jean-François Geleyn :
https://doi.org/10.1142/9781783266913_0026 <http://arxiv.org/abs/1510.03239>
- * The 2017 and 2018 JAS papers about the use of θ_S to describe the energetics of tropical cyclones :
<http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/abs/10.1175/JAS-D-17-0126.1> <https://arxiv.org/abs/1704.06098>
<https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/JAS-D-18-0126.1> <https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.00834>
- * The 2019 two-parts papers in La Météorologie (in French) :
<https://doi.org/10.4267/2042/70558> <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.11696>
<https://doi.org/10.4267/2042/70559> <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.11699>
- * The 2022 JAS paper written with Bjorn Stevens :
<https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-21-0095.1> <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.01376>
- * The 2022 paper about data assimilation written with Jean-François Mahfouf and Pauline Martinet (in particular)
<https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-15-2021-2022> <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.05883>
- * My last 2022 report about θ_S » and $PV(\theta_S)$ on arXiv : <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.10092>

2) Isobaric Charts of « theta-s » θ_s

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Figures 1 and 2 show that it is possible to obtain roughly the same visual impressions for the isobaric maps of θ'_w and θ_s , although the color scale and isolines need to be readjusted. In particular, warm sectors corresponding to "iso- $\theta'_w = 14^\circ\text{C}$ " appear to correspond to "iso- $\theta_s = 30^\circ\text{C}$ " at 850 hPa.

The fact that these isobaric maps are quite similar indicates that the entropy of moist air (measured with θ_s) is a marker of air masses horizontally at least as good as the pseudo-adiabatic variable θ'_w (which is much more complex and computationally expensive in models outputs). The variable θ_s also clearly highlights frontal zones, warm sectors (orange-red), cold air descents to the north of the domain (blue), etc.

However, since this adjustment of the palettes must be made differently for each level, this should induce more marked differences in the vertical sections of these two variables θ'_w and θ_s (see other Tutorials).

Figure 1. Charts for MSLP (isolines) and potential temperatures at 900 hPa (colored areas) for October 17, 2012 12 UTC (M2 internship of E. Blot, 2013 ; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

Figure 2. Charts for MSLP (isolines) and potential temperatures at 850 hPa (colored areas) for September 21, 2011 r00-p03h. Color version of Figure 1 p.920 of Marquet (2014, QJRMS, pp. 917-929, Vol. 140, Vol. 140 ; <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>).

3) Vertical cross-sections of « theta-s » θ_s across fronts

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The vertical cross-sections of the variables θ'_w and θ_s are quite different in the moist lower layers, where, for the moist-air entropy (and θ_s), the factor close to "6" derived from the third law of thermodynamics induces isentropic zones (θ_s almost constant in the lower layers (see vertical black arrows). Conversely, θ'_w shows a marked minimum around 800 to 850 hPa with warmer values near the ground. This more uniform appearance of θ_s throughout the boundary layer should allow for a better understanding of air masses with θ_s , and this closer to the ground, with the positioning of surface fronts being facilitated by using θ_s .

In the frontal zones (colored, almost pseudo-adiabatic), it is shown that θ'_w is logically almost constant from the ground to 700 or 600 hPa, while the moist-air entropy (θ_s) is only constant in the boundary layer and increases above it. In the fronts we observe a kind of "fuzzie" or "suction" of isentropes (θ_s) by convection (blue arrows), a property that also exists in the leading part of squall lines and in the walls and spiral bands of cyclones (see the corresponding Tutorial).

Figure 1. Left: MSLP and θ'_w map at 850 hPa with ARPEGE (cross-section in red) for September 21, 2011 r00-p03h. **Above:** the vertical cross-sections of θ'_w and θ_s . Color versions of Figures 1 and 3 p.920-921 of Marquet (2014, QJRM, p.917-929, Vol. 140; <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>).

Figure 2. Left: ANASYG (with cross-section) for a disturbance east of Newfoundland on January 8, 2013 at 00 UTC. **Above:** vertical cross-sections of θ'_w and θ_s with ARPEGE. Final year project of E. Blot (2013; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

4) Vertical cross-sections of « theta-s » θ_s for a « split front »

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For the split front shown in Figure 1 and simulated with the AROME CRM model, the vertical cross-sections of the variables θ'_w and θ_s are very different in the moist lower layers (below approximately 500 hPa). The factor close to "6" derived from the third law of thermodynamics in the formula of the moist-air entropy variable θ_s (see the first Tutorial) induces isentropic zones in the lower layers (i.e. with θ_s almost a constant, see vertical black arrows). Conversely, θ'_w shows a marked minimum around 800 hPa or 700 hPa in the cold sector on the left, with warmer values near the ground.

In frontal regions (colored, almost pseudo-adiabatic) θ'_w is logically almost constant from the ground up to 700 or 600 hPa, while entropy (θ_s) is only constant in the boundary layer and increases above it. In the upper-level frontal regions, we observe a kind of "swirl" or "suction" of isentropes (θ_s) by convection (blue arrows), a property that also exists for simple fronts, in the leading part of squall lines, and in the walls and spiral bands of cyclones (see corresponding Tutorial).

The specificity of the cross-section for this split front and for θ_s (and therefore for the moist-air entropy), in addition to the " suction of isentropes" aspect in the convective part and the good representation of the cold air mass at the rear, is the kind of "sperm whale nose" which allows the upper-level front to be located, as indicated in the conceptual diagram designed by E. Blot, where the area where θ_s is homogeneous on the vertical (in yellow) is attributed to the effect of moist-air turbulence on the variable θ_s .

Figure 1. Bottom left: Radar reflectivity on February 14, 2013, at 12:00 UTC with cross-section (in red), surface cold front (dashed blue arrow) and upper-air cold front (solid blue arrow). **On the top:** Vertical cross-sections of θ'_w and θ_s with AROME (February 14, 2013, r00 p12h). **Bottom right:** Conceptual model. Final year project of E. Blot (2013 ; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

5) Vertical cross-sections for « theta-s » θ_s for a « squall line »

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The general feature for the front of the squall line simulated by AROME shown in the Figure 1 (vertical black line) is similar to the pattern for θ'_w and θ_s described in the Tutorial for a front. The impact on the moist-air entropy (and therefore θ_s) of the numerous convective cells located in the rear of the front correspond to several successive aspirations of the larger upper-troposphere values towards the middle troposphere (see the isoline in red and the orange areas which go down to 600 to 700 hPa).

In contrast, the values of the pseudo-adiabatic variable θ'_w are more homogeneous vertically in convective cells, but making the vertical section of θ'_w a little "confusing" in places, with a "noisy" aspect that is not found with θ_s (and therefore the moist-air entropy).

The conceptual diagram designed by E. Blot also reminds us that the "cold" values of θ_s located in the mid-troposphere (700-500 hPa, in light blue) can be more easily related to the same blue values located in the "cold region" in the lower-levels (850-1000 hPa), which extends below and behind this squall line. This effect is much less visible with the pseudo-adiabatic variable θ'_w , which loses some (or even a lot) of its meaning in unsaturated air and as soon as one leaves the precipitating updrafts regions.

6) Isobaric charts and vertical cross-sections of « theta-s » θ_s in a cyclone

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Since cyclones are the most intense, moistness, with the strongest thermal and dynamic contrasts on the planet, it was important to know how and what the differences are between the views of a cyclone seen through the pseudo-adiabatic variable θ'_w on the one hand, and the moist-air entropy and the variable θ_s on the other.

In the Figure 1 are show the 900 hPa isobaric charts of these two quantities. It can be seen that, by changing the color scale, the variable θ_s can be used to study the different air masses, just as is currently done with θ'_w . One can even discern with θ_s more pronounced contrasts between the spiral bands and their surroundings.

Figure 1. MSLP charts (isolines) for θ'_w and θ_s (colored areas) at 900 hPa for the cyclone “Dumilé” simulated with the ALADIN-Réunion model for January 3, 2013 r03-p00h.

From the internship of E. Blot (2013; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

Figure 2 shows the vertical cross-sections of the two quantities θ'_w and θ_s . As with the fronts, split front and squall line (see other Tutorials), we also observe here that the air masses are better defined in terms of the moist-air entropy and the variable θ_s than with the pseudo-adiabatic potential temperature θ'_w .

Indeed, the larger values of θ'_w in the lower layers are overcome by a relative minimum of θ'_w around 700 to 500 hPa, while θ_s has a relative minimum near the ground (around 850 to 900 hPa) for each of the vertical columns, with almost homogeneous values of θ_s in the boundary layer up to 800 to 700 hPa (see the black arrows), before θ_s grows systematically in the upper troposphere.

As with the fronts and squall lines, we can see that the two walls of the eye (solid black lines) and the two spiral bands (dotted black lines) are clearly visible with θ_s and are located through the “isentropes aspirations” (blue arrows).

Figure 2. Vertical cross-sections between 49°E and 60°E (at 18.5°S) for the variables θ'_w and θ_s for the cyclone “Dumilé” simulated with the ALADIN-Réunion model for January 3, 2013 r00-p12h (final year project of E. Blot, 2013; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>) with extended and colorized versions of the vertical cross-sections from the energy study of this “Dumilé” cyclone published in Marquet (2017, JAS, Vol. 74, pp. 3451–3471) <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-17-0126.1> ; <https://arxiv.org/abs/1704.06098>).

7) The moist-air potential vorticity « $PV(\theta-s)$ » $PV(\theta_s)$ in the fronts

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The current form of the potential vorticity was defined by Hans Ertel as $PV(\psi)$ in terms of a general variable " ψ " where, in different articles published in 1942, Ertel indicated that ψ could be: the wind components, the total water content, the entropy or the associated potential temperature.

The current outputs of ARPEGE and AROME correspond to the quantity $PV(\theta)$ which uses the dry-air potential temperature θ , which is directly related to the entropy " s " of dry air through the Bauer's relationship $s = c_{pd} \ln(\theta) + s_0$, where c_{pd} (about 1005 J/K/kg) and s_0 are two constants.

Symmetric instability theories (see the corresponding Tutorial) use the pseudo-adiabatic variables θ'_w or θ_e , which have the drawback of not being directly related to the moist-air entropy. The consequences of using the variable $\psi = \theta_s$ (see the first Tutorial and the article Marquet, 2011, QJRMS, pp. 768-791, Vol. 137) in Ertel's formula were studied in the article Marquet (2014, QJRMS, pp. 917-929, Vol. 140), where the variable θ_s represents the moist-air entropy (as expected by Ertel) via the same Bauer's relationship valid for dry air, but generalized to the moist-air: $s = c_{pd} \ln(\theta_s) + s_0$, where c_{pd} and s_0 are the two same constants.

Figures 1 to 7 below (both the isobaric charts and the vertical cross-sections) show that:

- values of the 3 versions $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$ are the same above the 600 or 500 hPa level, where the water content is small, with therefore the same upper-level dynamic properties for the three quantities (foliation of the tropopause, tropospheric intrusion of large values of PV, etc) ;
- the differences between $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$ are more important in the lower levels, where the water content is larger and where $PV(\theta_e)$ becomes mostly negative and of opposite sign of $PV(\theta)$, whereas for the moist-air entropy $PV(\theta_s)$ exhibits more moderate values closer to 0 PVU ;
- the fact that the values of $PV(\theta_s)$ are less frequently negative than those for $PV(\theta_e)$ (in the northern hemisphere) is an interesting feature, because too frequent or too large negative values of $PV(\theta_e)$ (in the northern hemisphere) may induce issues in the algorithms of inversion of $PV(\theta_e)$;
- the regions with negative values of $PV(\theta_s)$ (in the northern hemisphere) seems to be correlated with the cold fronts and with the slantwise convection (or symmetric instability, see the corresponding Tutorial) that cannot be revealed by the usual formulation $PV(\theta)$ of Arpege and Arome, whereas $PV(\theta_e)$ is almost everywhere too negative (in the northern hemisphere) and likely prevents $PV(\theta_e)$ to be relevant for labeling the relevant regions of slantwise convection (or symmetric instability).

Figure 1. MSLP charts (isolignes) and potential vorticity units at 950 hPa (color scales) for (from the left to the right): $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$. Note that here (in the northern hemisphere) $PV(\theta)$ is mostly positive (yellow/green) and $PV(\theta_e)$ mostly negative (blue), with $PV(\theta_s)$ more frequently close to 0 PVU except close to the cold fronts (negative/blue regions) and close to the warm fronts and occlusions (positive/green-yellow). ARPEGE run of 8th of January 2013 r00-p00h. Internship of E. Blot (2013 ; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

Figure 2. A conceptual vision of low-levels values of $PV(\theta_s)$ in the Northern hemisphere (from the M2 internship of E. Blot, 2013 ; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

Figure 3. Isobaric charts of potential vorticity at 700 hPa (color scale) for: $PV(\theta)$ on the left, $PV(\theta_s)$ at the center, $PV(\theta_e)$ on the right. Outputs for the « Dumilé » cyclone simulated with the ALADIN-Réunion model (3rd of January 2013 r00-p03h). Note that, here in the Southern Hemisphere, $PV(\theta)$ is mostly negative and $PV(\theta_e)$ mostly positive, whereas the absolute moist-air entropy values of $PV(\theta_s)$ are closer to zero, except for the eye wall and the spiral bands (from the M2 internship E. Blot, 2013 ; <https://zenodo.org/record/6396371#.YlxWZ6Z5uV4>).

Figure 4. Isobaric charts of MSLP (black lines) and θ'_w at 850 hPa (color scale), with the potential vorticities labeled with blue and red lines (for positive versus negative PV values). Average (900+925+950 hPa) low-level values for: $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$. ARPEGE run for the 21th of September 2011 (r00-p12h). Here, in the Northern Hemisphere, $PV(\theta)$ is mostly positive (blue lines) and $PV(\theta_e)$ mostly negative (red lines), with $PV(\theta_s)$ closer to the zero value and

with less blue or red lines, except along the cold fronts (negative values in blue) and warm fronts or occlusions (positive values in red).

Color version of the Figures 8 (p.925) of Marquet (2014, QJRMS, p.917-929, Vol. 140 ; <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>).

Figure 5. Isobaric charts of MSLP (black lines every 2 hPa) and potential vorticities at 850 hPa (lines and color scales) for: $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$. ARPEGE forecast for the 21th of September 2011 (r00-p03h). $PV(\theta)$ is mostly positive (yellow and orange) and $PV(\theta_e)$ is mostly negative (in blue), with $PV(\theta_s)$ closer to the zero values (except close to the warm and cold fronts with positive and negative values). The dashes black arrows indicate the localization of the next cross-sections. Color version of the Figures 4 (p.922) of Marquet (2014, QJRMS, p.917-929, Vol. 140 ; <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>).

Figure 6. Vertical cross-sections of the potential vorticities (isolines and color scales) for: $PV(\theta)$, $PV(\theta_s)$ and $PV(\theta_e)$. ARPEGE forecast for the 21th of September 2011 (r00-p03h). The 3 PV almost superimpose in the dry upper-level regions (above the 600 hPa level), with low-level positive values of $PV(\theta)$ (yellow+orange), low-level very negative values of $PV(\theta_e)$ (blue) and low-level moderate values of $PV(\theta_s)$ for the absolute entropy, for which the sole negative regions (in blue) are localized along the cold fronts (blue bold lines).

Color versions of the Figures 5 (p.923) of Marquet (2014, QJRMS, p.917-929, Vol. 140 ; <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.2379>).

Figure 7. *On the left* : the French ANASYG for the 7th of December 2021 at 12UTC, with the “BARRA” storm and the black-dashed line indicating the localization of the next cross-sections. *Above*: vertical cross-sections at 46°N (between 11.5°W and 15.5°E) with the potential vorticity (color scales) for: $PV(\theta)$ on the top and $PV(\theta_s)$ on the center. Output for ARPEGE (on the left) and AROME (on the right) for the 12 hour forecast from r00. The upper regions boxed in dashed green are those where the two variables $PV(\theta)$ and $PV(\theta_s)$ almost superimpose, and

where the same stratospheric intrusions correspond to the green arrows.

Figures from the talk at the “Ateliers Prévi-GMAP” of Pascal Marquet (April 2022)

[http://controle.meteo.fr/docs_et_publics/Presentations/AteliersPREVIGMAP/atelier_2022-01-24/](http://controle.meteo.fr/docs_et_publics/Presentations/AteliersPREVIGMAP/atelier_2022-01-24/Marquet_previgmap_24.01.2022_theta-s.pdf)

[Marquet_previgmap_24.01.2022_theta-s.pdf](http://controle.meteo.fr/docs_et_publics/Presentations/AteliersPREVIGMAP/atelier_2022-01-24/Marquet_previgmap_24.01.2022_theta-s.pdf) et la version étendue (en anglais)

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.10092>

8) Instabilité symétrique / convection en pente.

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There are different types of instabilities affecting atmospheric motions. First, there is baroclinic instability, which, for large-scale disturbances and flows, is classically studied using quasi-horizontal iso- θ surfaces, that is, surfaces where the dry air potential temperature θ is a constant. Then there is (quasi) vertical instability, which, for convective cells and frontal regions, is usually assessed by examining the emagram and is characterized by movements controlled by vertical gradients of the pseudo-adiabatic potential temperature (θ'_w).

But the search for an explanation for certain intense rain bands has brought to light another type of instability called "symmetrical", to try to explain the associated areas of "slantwise convection", with intermediate inclinations between the quasi-horizontal ones of the disturbances (iso- θ) and the quasi-vertical ones of the convective cells (iso- θ'_w).

Figure 1. The figure 2 (p.290) of Bennetts and Hoskins (QJRMS, p.945-962, 1979), with additional informations (color features).

The original vision of Bennetts and Hoskins is recalled in Figure 1, where, in addition to the two surfaces iso- θ and iso- θ'_w (in green), the iso-M (momentum) surface, which is parallel to the vorticity vector (in blue), is considered. The competition between the two instabilities -thermal (iso- θ'_w) and dynamic (iso-M)- would lead to the “tilted/inclined/slantwise” circulation A/B/C (in red).

Figure 2. The figure 5a (p. 2720) of Schultz and Schumacher (MWR, p.2709-2732, 1999) + corrigendum (p.1573, 2000)

The synthesis by Schultz and Schumacher (1999), shown in Figure 2, represents a schematic cross-section of a moist symmetric instability in a mid-latitude mesoscale front or convective system [adapted from Seman (1991, 1992)]. The cloud (in gray) is surrounded by the thick solid line. The downward-sloping line

represents the orientation of the typical cold air potential temperature contour (θ). The other lines with arrows represent vertical and slantwise circulations. The hatching is proportional to the precipitation intensity. Moist gravitational instability is released along the vertical line corresponding to pure convection, while moist symmetric instability is released along the oblique line associated with precipitation.

Figure 3. The figure 5b (p. 2720) of Schultz and Schumacher (MWR, p.2709-2732, 1999)

The synthesis of Schultz and Schumacher (1999) recalled in Figure 3 represents the scheme of the symmetric convective instability in a warm front as described in the "escalator-elevator" model (Neiman et al. 1993, Fig. 8).

Figure 4. The figure 4 (p.2718) of Schultz and Schumacher (MWR p.2709-2732, 1999), which is based on a Figure previously drawn by James Moore and Sean Nolan.

Another synthesis by Schultz and Schumacher (1999), shown in Figure 4, represents the stability regimes often observed near frontal areas. The thick contours (in black) represent the "iso-M" lines, and the thinner isolines (in gray) represent the iso- θ_e lines (which are also almost iso- θ'_w lines). The "CSI" ("Conditional Symmetric Instability") region, outlined in red, is where the iso-M lines are more inclined than the iso- θ_e or iso- θ'_w lines.

Figure 5. A Figure adapted from a slide extracted from an M2 course by Bernard Legras (IPSL/LMD), himself taking a figure from Houze (1993). English translations of the legends (from top to bottom) are:

- B. Legras : M2 course “Clouds and Fronts” (solid blue line boxed)
- Symmetric Instability generating bands of precipitations (yellow filled boxed)
- region with negative values of $PV(\theta_e)$ (red dashed line boxed)
- R. A. Houze (1993) (gray filled boxed)

Figure 5 represents the area (circled in red) where the criteria described above for "symmetric instability" are met (iso-M more steeply inclined than iso- θ_e), linked to intense rainfall bands far from the surface frontal zone. This criterion is translated here in terms of negative zones for the moist potential vorticity $PV(\theta_e)$, where, compared to the usual potential vorticity $PV(\theta)$, the dry air potential temperature (θ) has been replaced by the equivalent potential temperature (θ_e).